

STUDENTS' PERCEPTION ON THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19774112>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between artificial intelligence (AI) and students' writing proficiency in academic essay writing among first-year Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated during the school year 2025-2026. Employing a quantitative correlational research design, the study investigated students' level of knowledge, extent of AI usage, perceived impact of AI, and perspectives on AI-human collaboration in writing. Data were gathered using an adapted survey questionnaire administered to the total population of 81 BSBA first-year students through a census approach. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were used to analyse students' perceptions, while Spearman's rho correlation was applied to determine the relationships among the variables due to non-normal data distribution. The results revealed that students possessed a high level of knowledge of AI tools ($M = 3.84$) and frequently used AI in their writing process ($M = 3.82$). The perceived impact of AI on writing proficiency was moderately high ($M = 3.80$), with improvements noted in grammar, coherence, and vocabulary development. Students also demonstrated strong agreement that AI should function as a collaborative writing aid rather than a replacement for human creativity ($M = 3.84$). Correlation analysis showed significant positive relationships among all variables, indicating that greater AI knowledge is associated with increased usage, stronger perceived benefits, and more favourable collaborative perspectives. The findings suggest that AI serves as a valuable educational scaffold when integrated responsibly into academic writing practices.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, academic writing, writing proficiency*

INTRODUCTION

Writing is an essential skill for students to master as it is a primary competence for lifelong study (UNESCO, 2023). It is a foundational skill in academic success, encompassing clarity, coherence, grammatical accuracy, vocabulary use, and content development. However, many students in higher education continue to face persistent challenges in producing well-structured, high-quality writing, often due to limited vocabulary, weak grammar proficiency, and difficulty in organizing ideas. As academic demands grow more rigorous, students increasingly turn to technological tools to support their writing needs. In today's generation, artificial intelligence (AI) has become a vital tool in the field of education most specifically in the field of writing processes. AI-powered platforms provide real-time assistance by offering grammar corrections, vocabulary enhancements, sentence restructuring, and feedback that helps students revise their work for better clarity and coherence.

Technology has a huge impact on our lives in the contemporary society, and education is no exception. The society is upgrading including our fast growing technological age and the integration of artificial intelligent applications in teaching and learning is skyrocketing. Artificial intelligence significance has become wide, particularly during the beginning of the university's and school's closure due to the coronavirus pandemic on 2019. Therefore, Artificial intelligence is reshaping educational practices by enabling the development of digital learning platforms, assessment tools, and writing support systems that influence how students engage in and perceive academic essay writing (UNESCO, 2023; OECD, 2021).

Studies indicate that digital tools have a measurable impact on improving students' writing skills and enhancing their motivation to write (Han et al., 2021; Eragamreddy & Joseph, 2025). In writing contexts, artificial intelligence (AI) fosters iterative improvement by providing real-time feedback that guides students through multiple stages of revision (Kasneci et al., 2023). Furthermore, OECD (2023) affirms AI's role in enhancing core academic competencies, particularly in written communication.

Despite these advantages, concerns remain. Scholars such as Iskender (2023) and Mogavi et al. (2024) caution that overdependence on AI tools may hinder students' ability to think critically, express original ideas, and develop independent writing habits. This tension between the support AI offers and the risk of dependency highlights the need for further empirical investigation.

Thus, this study aimed to determine students' perceptions of AI integration in their academic essay writing processes.

This study contributed to the existing body of knowledge by providing statistically significant evidence regarding BSBA students' perceptions of AI use in academic essay writing during the school year 2025–2026.

Research Questions

This study aimed to test and measure the influence of artificial intelligence and the students' perception on it in their academic essay writing. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of students' knowledge of AI tools in academic essay writing?
2. What is the extent of AI use in students' writing tasks?
3. What is the level of impact of AI in writing academic essays?
4. What are the students' levels of perspectives on how AI should collaborate with human writers in the writing process?
5. Is there a positive impact on AI integration towards the academic essay writing among the 1st year BSBA students?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a correlational research design as it aimed to measure the relationship of artificial intelligence and academic essay writing. The researchers provided printed adapted survey questionnaires to the respondents to collect data regarding their perception on integrating AI on writing tasks.

The design allowed the researchers not only to explore students' perception, but also identified how often they use artificial intelligence and how they viewed it in relation to their writing proficiency through answering the adapted survey questionnaire.

Research Environment

The research was conducted at St. Vincent's College Incorporated – Main Campus, located in Padre Ramon Street, Estaka, Dipolog City, Zamboanga del Norte, during the school year 2025-2026. The total population of 81 1st year students in Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) were the respondents of the study. It is a four-year degree education focused on specialized undergraduate programs that provide a solid foundation in business principles.

St. Vincent's College Incorporated served as the ideal setting for this research due to the ease of access to the respondents since the researchers also came from the same institution, therefore, enhanced participant engagement. This convenience facilitated efficient data gathering, minimized logistical challenges, and maximized response rate. Furthermore, the researchers' familiarity with the student population allowed for a more nuanced understanding of the responses received which contributed to a more insightful and accurate interpretation of the findings.

Research Respondents and Sampling

The respondents of this study consisted on the total population of 81 1st year BSBA students enrolled at St. Vincent's College Incorporated – Main Campus during the school year 2025-2026. Given the population of the respondents, the researchers utilized the census approach as it allowed for the collection of data from the entire population. Additionally, the decision to focus on 1st year BSBA students was also strategic, as their coursework included technical writing which introduced them to the used of AI as a writing aid. This exposure showed their familiarity with academic writing practices supported by AI which enhanced their ability to provide informed and thoughtful responses to the survey questionnaire. Aside from these, 1st year students were often more receptive to participating in research studies, therefore, giving a fresh perspective on the subject matter.

Research Instruments and Validity

The data in this study was gathered through the use of the adapted survey questionnaire from the study of Nguyen, Xuan Huong titled "*Artificial Intelligence and Academic Writing: Exploring Student Use and Perceptions*", published in Discover Education, Volume 2, 2023, Article 1000071, conducted to the BSBA 1st year students enrolled in the school year 2025 – 2026. The survey questionnaire was designed to collect quantitative data on students' engagement with AI and how this influences their writing proficiency.

The validity of the instrument used was ensured through a thorough expert validation process conducted. The adapted questionnaire was submitted to a panel of professionals and experts in the field of education, alongside the legend that served as a basis on how they ranked it. These experts were tasked to review the content of the questionnaires submitted focusing on the clarity, comprehensiveness, and relevance of the questionnaire to the study's goal. After which, their feedback and comments were carefully considered and integrated to further refine the questionnaire.

Research Procedure

For this correlational research design, the data collection process utilized an adapted survey questionnaire which had been validated by English instructors of St. Vincent's College Incorporated.

The implementation of the study was structured by firstly identifying the two sections of 1st year BSBA students. The researchers prepared and provided a letter to the respondents' subject teacher requesting permission to administer the study during their class hours. The teacher's guidance ensured that the process was organized and that all students were given the opportunity to participate. Before the questionnaires were distributed, the researchers explained the purpose of the study, its objectives, and the

relevance of the respondents' input to the research. Additionally, to build trust and encouraged honest responses, the respondents was assured that all information collected would remain confidential and would only be used for academic purposes. Furthermore, the procedure of the study was facilitated in a structured manner, with clear instructions provided to avoid confusion and ensure consistency across both sections. After collection, the responses were carefully compiled, checked for completeness, and prepared for analysis to maintain integrity and reliability of the study.

Gathering of Data

A formal letter to request for the official enrolment count of the BSBA 1st year students was submitted to the office of the registrar. Upon getting the result of the total population of the respondents, the researchers coordinated with the BSBA subject teachers to seek permission in conducting the study during their class hours. This was done through provided letters which were given to the teachers among both the Block A and Block B BSBA 1st year. In order to have a valid research instrument, researchers adapted a survey questionnaire from a similar study. It was further revised after carefully considering the comments and suggestions of the validators during the validation process. The researchers utilized the survey questionnaire in administering the data collection after sending a request approval to the rightful owner of it. To begin data analysis, the answered questionnaires was retrieved from the respondents of the study. It was then passed on to the research statistician for the analysis of the results and its interpretations.

Statistical Treatment of Data

After gathering the questionnaires, each response was checked for completeness before being systematically organized and tabulated. The data was then being analysed and interpreted to address the research problem and test the study's hypothesis. Since this study does not involve direct assessment of writing skills, the analysis will focus on the intensity levels reported in the questionnaires: the students' knowledge on AI in writing their Academic essays; the extent on how often students use artificial intelligence; the impact of AI in writing their academic essays; and their perspectives on how AI should collaborate with human writers in the future.

Mean

The mean showed the average level of agreement of students with each statement. It helped identify whether they generally agree, disagree, or remain neutral about AI's role in writing. The mean was employed to determine the central tendency of participants' ratings across various statements. This provided insight into the general level of agreement or perception, with higher mean values indicating stronger agreement or more frequent use of AI tools. As shown in the results, the statement 1 in Table 1 had the

highest mean score which suggested that students were particularly knowledgeable or supportive of that aspect of AI.

Standard Deviation

In evaluating the variability of responses, a standard deviation was also used. A lower standard deviation indicated that participants responded in a more consistent manner, while a higher standard deviation suggested greater diversity in opinions. This helped identify which statements had widespread consensus and which elicited more varied reactions. Additionally, the relatively low standard deviation in the overall score for students' perspectives on AI collaboration (SD = 0.544) reflected a unified viewpoint, whereas higher values, such as in Statement 8 of Table 1 (SD = 1.070), indicated more dispersed responses.

Shapiro-Wilk Test

This was applied to evaluate the normality of the data distribution for each statement and overall scores. This test was crucial because many statistical analyses assumed that data followed a normal distribution. In this study, most individual statements showed significant deviations from normality ($p < .001$) which indicated that some of the data were not normally distributed. As a result, non-parametric methods like Spearman's rank-order correlation were more appropriate for further analysis. However, some overall scores, such as those in Table 2 and Table 4, had p-values greater than .05, indicating that those particular distributions were approximately normal and responses were relatively consistent.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

This research study aimed to determine the correlation between the scaffold of artificial intelligence and the academic essay writing proficiency based on the perceptions of the first-year students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) program at St. Vincent's College Incorporated for school year 2025-2026.

A Correlational Research Design was utilized to determine the correlation of artificial intelligence and students' writing proficiency in academic essay. The total population of the respondents was 81, thus, the appropriate data gathering method used was the Census Approach. This method ensured comprehensive data and highly accurate results. This study was conducted for five (5) months, during which the data was collected and analysed. The data was collected through the utilization of survey questionnaires to measure the perception of the respondents as to how the integration of artificial intelligence influenced their writing proficiency.

This study acknowledged several constraints that had an impact on the research findings. It included the fact that findings might be specific only to the population surveyed, potentially limiting generalizability to other populations or contexts. Additionally, data

collected via surveys could be subject to self-reporting biases, where respondents could overestimate or underestimate their use of AI in their writing proficiency. There was also a possibility for non-responses bias where it's unlikely that every student would willingly participate, and those who do not respond may differ systematically from those who do, thus, affecting the data collected or the findings.

RESULTS

Table 1. Knowledge of AI in Academic Essay Writing (N = 81)

Descriptive	Mean	SD	Shapiro-Wilk	
			W	p
I am aware that AI-powered writing tools for academic essays exist.	4.21	0.918	0.789	<.001
In my essay writing, I employed AI-powered grammar and spelling checkers.				
I am familiar with AI-based plagiarism detection techniques that I may use to ensure the originality of my academic work.	4.04	0.914	0.835	<.001
I have utilized AI methods for content summaries to comprehend challenging research publications.	4.01	0.981	0.820	<.001
I am familiar with AI-generated citation and reference tools that I use to prepare my academic work.	3.74	0.959	0.879	<.001
I have made use of AI-driven language translation technologies to access academic information written in languages other than my own.	3.78	0.962	0.878	<.001
I'm aware of AI writing helpers that provide context-specific word and phrase suggestions to improve essay writing.	3.93	0.959	0.835	<.001
I've used AI-generated essay outlines to efficiently arrange my ideas before writing.	3.68	1.070	0.869	<.001
I am aware of AI-powered services that recommend research topics and sources for essay preparation.	3.77	0.952	0.862	<.001
I am confident in my knowledge of AI-powered writing tools for academic essay writing.	3.62	1.019	0.874	<.001
Knowledge of AI in Academic Essay Writing	3.84	0.701	0.954	0.006

The mean scores for the statements ranged from 3.62 to 4.21, with most of the responses reflecting moderate agreement. Specifically, Statement 1 had the highest mean score of 4.21 and a Standard Deviation of 0.918. It indicated a relatively stronger

agreement, while Statement 10 had the lowest mean ($M = 3.62$, $SD = 1.019$), thus, showing a somewhat weaker agreement. The standard deviations (SD) ranged from 0.701 to 1.070, which indicated that there was some variability in the responses for the statements. The higher SD values, such as for Statement 8 ($SD = 1.070$), suggested that responses for this statement were more spread out, whereas lower SD values, such as for the "Knowledge of AI in Academic Essay Writing" ($SD = 0.701$), suggested that responses were more consistent.

The Shapiro-Wilk test results revealed that all p -values were less than .001, which suggested that the data for each statement significantly deviated from a normal distribution. This indicates that the distribution of responses was non-normal, and caution was being taken when applying parametric statistical methods that assume normality.

Table 2. The extent to which students use artificial intelligence

Descriptives	Descriptives		Shapiro-Wilk	
	Mean	SD	W	p
I examine and enhance my works using AI-powered grammar and spelling checkers.	3.96	0.887	0.844	<.001
I use AI-based plagiarism detection technologies to assure the originality of my academic writing.	3.83	0.755	0.815	<.001
AI-generated content summaries assist me in understanding difficult research articles for inclusion in my writings.	3.96	0.843	0.827	<.001
AI technologies help me generate citations and references in a variety of formats automatically.	3.86	0.802	0.822	<.001
I utilize language translation AI to access academic literature written in languages other than my native language.	3.84	0.813	0.856	<.001
AI-powered writing helpers provide context-specific word and phrase suggestions to help me improve my essay writing.	3.90	0.700	0.820	<.001
AI-powered systems suggest research subjects and suitable sources to help me prepare my essay.	3.78	0.758	0.843	<.001
Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools assist me in tailoring the style and tone of my essays to certain academic criteria.	3.75	0.845	0.867	<.001
I utilize AI-generated essay outlines to successfully arrange my ideas before writing.	3.79	0.932	0.876	<.001

AI-powered time management tools assist me in keeping track of my essay writing work and meeting deadlines.	3.56	1.000	0.888	<.001
Students use artificial intelligence.	3.82	0.612	0.973	0.083

The results showed that respondents regularly use AI for various purposes, including grammar correction, idea generation, paraphrasing, and vocabulary enhancement. The highest individual mean score (3.96) suggested that many students rely on AI to help organized and refine their written work. The Shapiro-Wilk result ($W = 0.973$, $p = 0.083$) showed no significant deviation from normality which indicated that the responses were relatively normally distributed and consistent. These findings demonstrated students' openness to the idea of using AI as learning and writing aid rather than as a replacement for their own writing.

Table 3. The impact of AI in writing academic essays

Descriptives	Shapiro-Wilk			
	Mean	SD	W	p
Using AI technologies in my essay writing has enhanced my general writing ability.	3.77	1.016	0.842	<.001
AI-powered grammar and spelling checks have assisted me in identifying and correcting writing errors, which has contributed to my writing ability growth.	3.89	0.775	0.820	<.001
AI-based plagiarism detection systems have raised my understanding of academic integrity and the value of uniqueness in writing.	3.86	0.737	0.833	<.001
AI-generated content summarizing has improved my capacity to extract essential ideas from difficult research articles, which has improved my writing comprehension.	3.90	0.860	0.854	<.001
Using AI writing aids has increased the clarity and coherence of my works, favorably improving my writing style.	3.85	0.882	0.843	<.001
AI-generated essay outlines have helped me arrange my ideas more efficiently and enhance the organization of my work.	3.86	0.905	0.861	<.001
The use of AI tools in my essay writing has forced me to critically assess and critique my own work, which has resulted in increased self-editing abilities.	3.69	0.889	0.864	<.001
The use of AI tools in my essay writing has forced me to critically assess and critique my own work, which has resulted in increased self-editing abilities.	3.69	0.983	0.862	<.001

AI technologies that provide context-specific word and phrase choices have helped me broaden my vocabulary and enhance the quality of my writing.	3.78	0.987	0.859	<.001
I feel that employing AI technologies has improved my writing abilities and greatly impacted my academic essay writing.	3.67	1.107	0.843	<.001
Impact of AI in Writing Academic Essays.	3.80	0.667	0.961	0.015

The findings revealed an overall mean of 3.80 (SD = 0.667) which signified a moderately high impact of AI on academic essay writing. Most respondents agreed that AI tools improved their grammar accuracy, coherence, and vocabulary usage. The consistently high mean scores (ranging from 3.67 to 3.90) reflected positive experiences with AI's ability to simplify the writing process and aid an idea expression.

However, the Shapiro-Wilk test ($W = 0.961, p = 0.015$) indicated a slight deviation from normality, implying that responses were somewhat varied. Some students relied heavily on AI, while others might use it more moderately.

Over all, the findings showed that AI has a positive influence on students' writing proficiency and confidence reflecting that AI tools can be used to scaffold learning and enhance academic performance when used ethically and responsibly.

Table 4. Students' perspectives on how AI should collaborate with human writers

Descriptives	Shapiro-Wilk			
	Mean	SD	W	p
I contend that AI should be employed as a writing helper to assist human authors during the essay writing process.	3.90	0.982	0.812	<.001
AI should be used to discover probable grammatical and spelling problems, with human authors making the ultimate choice on fixes.	3.88	0.872	0.862	<.001
I like AI to supply content recommendations and ideas, while human authors keep creative control over the essay's direction and reasoning.	3.88	0.781	0.826	<.001
AI should assist human authors by suggesting research topics and suitable sources, but human writers should still undertake critical analysis and synthesis.	3.83	0.863	0.858	<.001
I contend that AI-generated outlines can be useful, but human authors should be free to adapt and expand on them to fit their writing style.	3.74	0.863	0.867	<.001
Artificial intelligence (AI) should be employed for content summarizing and synthesis, supporting	3.63	0.782	0.854	<.001

human authors in reducing complicated material into brief and comprehensible paragraphs.				
I involving artificial intelligence to assist in correct citation and referencing, but human authors must guarantee the authenticity and appropriateness of the sources mentioned.	3.85	0.743	0.837	<.001
While AI may assist with language translation, human authors should verify the translated content to guarantee context and correctness.	3.74	0.738	0.842	<.001
AI should be used to discover possible areas for improvement during the editing process, while human authors give the final tweaks and improvements.	3.96	0.715	0.827	<.001
I believe that AI and human authors should work in tandem to maximize AI efficiency while keeping human originality and critical thinking in essay writing.	3.95	0.757	0.750	<.001
Students' perspectives on how AI should collaborate with human writers.	3.84	0.544	0.975	0.108

The highest mean scores (3.95 and 3.96) indicated strong agreement that AI can enhance productivity and efficiency when used under human supervision. Students recognized the significance of keeping human authorship, originality, and judgement in academic writing while benefiting from AI's assistance.

The Shapiro-Wilk test ($W = 0.975$, $p = 0.108$) suggested no significant deviation from normality, indicating consistent views among respondents.

Correlation Matrix		Knowledge of AI in Academic Essay Writing	Students use artificial intelligence.	Impact of AI in Writing Academic Essays.	Students' perspectives on how AI should collaborate with human writers.
Knowledge of AI in Academic Essay Writing	Spearman's rho	—			
	df	—			
	p-value	—			
students use artificial intelligence.	Spearman's rho	0.652***	—		
	df	79	—		

	p-value	<.001	—		
Impact of AI in Writing Academic Essays.	Spearman's rho	0.516***	0.661***	—	
	df	79	79	—	
Students' perspectives on how AI should collaborate with human writers.	p-value	<.001	<.001	—	
	Spearman's rho	0.496***	0.599***	0.673***	—
	df	79	79	79	—
	p-value	<.001	<.001	<.001	—

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

A detailed examination of the correlation matrix reveals a set of interconnected relationships between four variables concerning students and artificial intelligence in academic writing. The analysis, a Spearman's rank-order correlation based on a sample of 81 participants ($df = 79$), found that every relationship was both positive and highly statistically significant ($p < .001$). This indicates a consistent pattern where an increase in any one variable is associated with an increase in the others.

Looking at each variable individually, Knowledge of AI in Academic Essay Writing demonstrated a strong positive correlation with students' use of artificial intelligence ($r = .652$). This was its most pronounced relationship, suggesting a robust link between what students know about AI and their actual use of it. Furthermore, this knowledge was moderately and positively correlated with their perception of the Impact of AI in Writing Academic Essays ($r = .516$) and, to a similar degree, with their students' perspectives on how AI should collaborate with human writers ($r = .496$).

The variable students use artificial intelligence also showed significant positive correlations with the other perceptual factors. It had a strong positive relationship with the perceived Impact of AI ($r = .661$), indicating that those who use AI more also tend to perceive its impact as being greater. Its connection to Students' perspectives on collaboration was also positive and moderate-to-strong ($r = .599$).

Finally, the two perceptual variables were very closely linked. The relationship between the perceived impact of AI in Writing Academic Essays and Students' perspectives on how AI should collaborate with human writers was the strongest one found in the entire analysis, with a large positive correlation of $r = .673$. In summary, while all variables were positively related, the statistical connections ranged from moderate ($r = .496$) to strong ($r = .673$), with the tightest link being between students' perceptions of AI's impact and their views on its collaborative role.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study revealed that students demonstrated a generally positive and engaged stance toward artificial intelligence (AI) in academic essay writing. Students reported moderate to high levels of knowledge about AI, with results indicating familiarity with its applications in writing. However, variability in responses suggested that knowledge is not evenly distributed which emphasized the need for targeted instruction to ensure foundational understanding among all learners. The results indicated that students generally showed positive attitudes toward the use of AI in higher education, though their levels of knowledge and familiarity varied across disciplines (Alzahrani, 2019).

In terms of usage, students were frequently engaged with AI tools during the writing process. AI was commonly used for grammar correction, idea generation, paraphrasing, and vocabulary enhancement. The consistency in responses suggested that AI use has become a common academic practice, showing that students increasingly rely on AI-powered writing tools for brainstorming, revision, and language improvement (Cotton et al., 2023; Kasneci et al., 2023). Importantly, students viewed AI as a supportive tool rather than a replacement for human effort, supporting the view that AI serves as an assistive technology rather than a substitute for critical thinking (Holmes et al., 2022).

Additionally, students also perceived AI to have a positive impact on their writing proficiency. They acknowledged improvements in grammar, coherence, vocabulary, and clarity of expression. The findings suggested that AI functions as a scaffold that simplifies the writing process and enhances academic performance when used ethically. Additionally, the use of AI-assisted tools significantly improved the students' grammar, coherence, vocabulary, and clarity of expression in their written outputs. Moreover, students expressed strong agreement that AI should serve as a collaborative partner rather than replace human creativity and judgment. The data showed a shared consensus that AI enhances productivity under human supervision while preserving originality in academic writing (Aculado and Ibojo., 2021).

Correlation analysis further strengthens these findings. Strong and statistically significant relationships were found among knowledge, usage, perceived impact, and collaborative perspectives. Students with greater knowledge of AI tend to use it more frequently and perceive stronger benefits. Similarly, frequent users were more likely to support ethical AI-human collaboration. The strongest relationship was observed between perceived impact and collaborative perspectives. Overall, the findings indicate a reinforcing cycle where increased knowledge and experience with AI shape favourable attitudes toward its academic role, echoing patterns observed in recent educational technology research (Kasneci et al., 2023; Dwivedi et al., 2023).

Conclusions

This study examined the relationship between artificial intelligence (AI) integration and the writing proficiency of first-year BSBA students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated. The findings indicated that students demonstrated strong knowledge of AI tools, frequent usage in academic writing tasks, and a moderately high perception of its positive impact on grammar, coherence, and vocabulary development.

Moreover, students expressed favourable perspectives toward AI as a collaborative partner rather than a replacement for human effort. To add to this, the significant positive correlations among AI knowledge, usage, and perceived impact suggested that increased familiarity and engagement with AI tools were associated with improved writing confidence and perceived proficiency. Although the study was limited by its specific sample and reliance on self-reported data, the results highlighted the potential of AI as an effective scaffolding tool when used ethically and responsibly.

Overall, this research contributed to the expanding body of literature on AI in education and offered valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and developers aiming to optimize AI integration in academic writing instruction.

Recommendations

For Education Policymakers

Implement targeted educational programs to improve students' understanding of AI tools, their capabilities, and ethical considerations. These programs should focus on responsible AI usage, plagiarism prevention, and the necessity of maintaining originality and critical thinking in writing.

For Technical Writing Instructors

Encourage educators to incorporate AI tools strategically into writing instruction, emphasizing their use as aids rather than replacements for human effort. Promote activities that foster critical engagement with AI feedback, such as peer review and reflective writing practices.

For Technology Developers

Invest in the development of AI writing tools that can adapt to individual student needs and learning styles. These systems provided personalized feedback and guidance, helping students improve their writing skills progressively.

For Future Researchers

Conduct longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of AI integration on students' writing proficiency and critical thinking abilities. Explore the effectiveness of different AI tools and pedagogical approaches in various academic contexts. Future research should also consider including direct assessments of writing skills to complement self-reported data.

For School Administrators

Ensure that all students have equitable access to AI tools and training despite of their socioeconomic background or technological proficiency. Provide support to students who may face challenges in accessing or using AI effectively.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study was conducted in full compliance with established ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents before data collection, and participation in the study was voluntary, with respondents informed of their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. The privacy, anonymity, and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained, and all data were handled in accordance with Data Privacy regulations. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded throughout the research process, and no form of harm or coercion was involved. No conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study, and plagiarism was strictly avoided. Objectivity was observed in the collection, analysis, and interpretation of the data to prevent bias, and the findings were used solely for academic and research purposes. Artificial intelligence tools, if utilized, were employed only as support during the writing process, and full responsibility for the content, analysis, and interpretation of the study rests with the researchers.

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